

From Nayaks to Zamindars :Transformation of Land Revenue Systems And Society In Bodinayakanur

Prof. S. PANDIYALAKSHMI ,Assistant professor of History,

Sri Vasavi College ,Erode ,Tamilnadu

Received: Oct 18 , 2025

Accepted: Nov 14, 2025

Published: Nov 15, 2025

Abstract : Indians followed traditional socio- economic fabric propitiated by exploitative poligary system. The officials of East India company found it difficult to enter into Indian economic system. Introduction of zamindari system in 1802 under the disguise of Permanent Revenue settlement which was introduced by Cornwallis. Chakku Nayak impressed the Raja by killing a ferocious wild boar which caused massive destruction for which heavy price was fixed. Their cultural dependence, their ruthless blind pursuit of caste system curtailed individualism. Zamindars of Madurai district mostly belong to Kambalathu of Thottiya Naicker community. The village revenue officer was called Maniyakaran or Ambalakaran. The collection from the Village was handed over to Makannan. Intercaste marriage was strictly prohibited ,violations were strictly dealt with ,rigid caste customs made woman submissive and isolated. The Economic, political, Social Non-comitance policies adopted by zamindars of Bodinayakaur made peasants suffer.

Key words : *Thenkasiyam pathi.- peshcush- Kambalathar- Non-comitance policies.*

Introduction:

Bodinayakanur is a major hub cardamom production , earning it the nick name as “ India’s Cardamom capital” and is a major cardamom growing region in Tamil Nadu. Stretches up to Andipatti canal in the east, Kuttikulam pudur in the south, Bodi Mettu region in the west, surrounded by the Korangani hills. Bodinayakanur zamin possess five Palaces which is called as Periya Aranmanai, kella machu Aranmanai, Mella machu Aranmanai, machu Aranmanai and kottathu Aranmanai

The assumption of direct administration in 1801 and introduction of zamindari system in 1802 under the disguise of Permanent Revenue settlement which was introduced by Cornwallis. The East India company created new system of land tenure based on Bengal system in different districts of Madras presidency¹.

In 1802 Madras Government begin to settle its province in zamindari estates along the lines of Permanent settlement in Bengal. There were chieftains and revenue farmers surviving from the Pre- British rule. Government auctioned the territories in Mittas (parcels). According to this mittadaras they have the same legal status as zamindar. It quickly collapsed due to inexperienced management and unrealistic revenue demands. Hence it was abandon in 1818. The next 30 years several estates got into difficulties and land settled under Ryotwari were dissolved. Tamil estates usually remained important the early 20th century estates covered nearly six million areas that is 19% of the total area of Tamilnadu. Estate owners also managed 7% of Tamil area held under *Inam*. Because of the modern wealth lineage and attention they controlled markets, temples and other facilities which catered for the whole population.

The system of land tenure was introduced by British in 1802. Which altered the basic life structure of the people of 19th century. This study gives a detailed picture of nature and implications of Zamindari system. When the British acquired the sovereignty of Madras Presidency in 1801, It was a tough task to understand our language customs and practices. With no proper survey and settlement their desire to exploit the Indian economy couldn't be fulfilled. Indians followed traditional socio economic fabric propitiated by exploitative poligary system. The officials of East India company found it difficult to enter into Indian economic system. The zamindars under zamindari system functioned as deciding factor in rural economy. In the age of illiteracy, ignorance and poverty based on caste hierarchy. The zamindari arrangement of

¹ Hodgson, member of Board of Revenue, settlement report on Dindugul, 20 March, 1808, M.C.R, Vol. 1254, P-32

revenue collection contributed to deterrent results. As the result of this inhuman system ,life of men and women in their jurisdiction turned out to be miserable. This contributed to emergence of socio political movements like freedom movement, peasant movement and worker movement leading to its final abolition.

Land Revenue formed the main source of income upon which the expenditure of the ruler rested. During Sangam period land tax formed the chief source of Revenue to the Government besides land Revenue customs duties were also levied on goods landing in the sea ports².

Under Nayaks the land Revenue system was the main source of public income for the collection of revenue land was divided into two halves. The first category of land was crown appointed officers who collected revenue. The village revenue officer was called Maniyakaran or Ambalakaran. The collection from the Village was handed over to Makannan. He remitted the amount to the king's treasury³.

The word Thennadu in Tamil ,means South India in English Thentamilagam in Tamil means regions south to Madurai. In South Tamilnadu the history of Madurai Nayaks is very important . Madurai, Trichy, Ramnad, Tirunelveli, Salem, Coimbatore, Trivancore were ruled by Viswanatha Nayak. This palayakar system was established in 1535 A. D. which was equivalent to the Fadal system of the British. It consist of 72 Palayams⁴.

Bodinayakanur Zamindars:

In Madurai district zamindari system was introduced by Nayaks of Madurai. One of the ancient zamindaries of Madurai district was Bodinayakanur zamindari. Centuries ago Bodinayakanur was called *Thenkasiyam pathi*. It was bordered on the north by the Palani hills on the west by Travancore hills and on the other two sides in villages in Periyakulam Taluk.

² Madras Information, Vol. IV, NO.5, May 1950, p.13.

³ Sathiyanaithaier R., History of the Nayaks of Madras, 1924, pp.. 243-245.

⁴ Jagavira Pandiyanar, Veera Sarithiram, 1934, p.14.

The original inhabitant emigrated from Anandapur district of Andrapradesh early in 14th century. The name of the original founder was Chakku Nayak⁵. This region was ruled by the Raja of Trivancore punaiattu Thambiran. Chakku Nayak impressed the Raja by killing a ferocious wild boar which caused massive destruction for which heavy price was fixed⁶. The Raja was delighted with the valour of the Nayak and conferred this estate upon him under one condition that hundred *pon* (Gold coins) was to be paid to the Raja on each time of the succession of new heir⁷.

Even after independence uptill 1948 giving presents to the Raja was in practice till 1948. In 1487 *Chilla Bodinayak* succeeded the estate and attained fame by his strength and bravery. He defeated an athlete Mallakhan who was the champion of the Vijayanagar kingdom. The ruler of Madurai Viswanatha Nayak honoured him by directing region ruled by Chilla Bodiyanak would be there after called as "Bodinayakanur". After Viswanatha Nayak conquered

the Madurai region it become one of the palayams under Nayaks of Madurai⁸. After this discreditable incident Dindugul fell in to hands of Hyder Ali. He confiscated the estate in 1755 British captured the province in 1790 and the Palayam was restored to Palayakar⁹. Thirumala Bodinayakan nurtured acrimony and restricted entry of collector Wynch when he first came to the district. Hence the British punished him by fixing 70% of the total income as taxes¹⁰.

⁵ P.B.R., No. 115, 17 January 1872.

⁶ Report of the Estate Land Act Committee, Part II. p.167.

⁷ Nagasamy. R.(ed), Palayappattukkalin Varalaru(Tamil), Vol.II, Madras, 1981, p.126

⁸ Baliga B.S.,Madras District Gazetteers, Madurai, Madras, 1960, p.422

⁹ Collector of Madurai, 24 November 1795, letter to the Board of Revenue, M.C.R. Vol.5160. pp. 237-238

¹⁰ Ibid.,24 April 1795,M.C.R.,Vol.1203,PP..203-213.

Bangaru Tirumalai Bodinayakan succeeded Tirumala Bodinayakan. He built an anaikatt across the kottakudi river at the cost of 4 lakh rupees and brought 4000 acres of wet land under cultivation.¹¹ He died in 1862 leaving the zamindari estate to *Kamaraja Pandiya Nayak* who was only three years old when his father died. This minor son became major in 1879. During this period he was introduced to western education by an English tutor in Madurai.¹² Subsequently accompanied by the tutor. He proceeded to Madras for his education.¹³ In 1880 his estate was recognized and a *Sansad* was issued to him. Kamaraja Pandiya Nayak was died in 1889. Leaving the estate to *Kamulammal* his young wife.¹⁴ She was known for her Philanthropy and women empowerment. She carried out public services constructed many choultries laid foundation for Victoria memorial elementary school and high school. She liberally contributed for education.¹⁵

In 1889 the cousin of late zamindar kamaraja Pandya Nayak filed a suit against Kamulammal and climbed the estate. In 1890 he was granted a subdivision named Dombucherry in consideration for his claim. In 1896 another subdivision named Pudhipuram was created and it was registered in the name of Vijayadhanthi Pathy Pandiyan Nayak another cousin of the late zamindar.¹⁶ The *peshcush*¹⁷ was Rupees 13,858 exclusively Dombucherry and Pudhipuram division.¹⁸

Kamulammal was died in 1921 and she was succeeded by Kamaraja Pandiya Nayak who was son of Kanthasamy Nayak. He served as member of Madras legislative council from 1930 to 1938 and

¹¹ Vadivelu, A., *The Ruling Chiefs, Nobles and Zamindars of India*, Madras, 1959, p.674

¹² P.B.R., No.2047, 3 March 1877.

¹³ Ibid., 3259, 1 December 1875.

¹⁴ G.O.No.1638, L.R.D. 14 September 1944.

¹⁵ Vadivelu A., *Op.cit.*, p.675.

¹⁶ G.O.No.262.R.d., 20 July 1896.

¹⁷ *Peshcush*, is the Revenue collected by East India Company from Zamindars.

¹⁸ Parker, Collector of Madurai, 24 August 1849, letter to the Board of Revenue, M,C,R. Vol.5345, p.322.

was a member legislative assembly from 1938 to his death until 1941. There after Raja Pandya Nayakar succeeded as zamindar to the estate.¹⁹

Customs and Practices:

The caste system formed the basic structure of Social Organization among zamindar. The society was mostly conservative and the customs formed the basics of social norms. Dogmatic religious traditions, lack of Social mobility, caste superiority, reduced their cultural independent. Their cultural dependence, their ruthless blind pursuit of caste system curtailed individualism. Zamindars of Madurai district mostly belong to *Kambalathu of Thottiya Naicker community*. They migrated from North India to Anandapur district in Andra Pradesh.²⁰ In the Vijayanagar Kingdom they were employed as military peon, when Vijayanagar rulers invaded Madurai, they came to South Tamil Nadu called Thennadu and settled in Madurai, Dindugul, Tirunelvely and Manaparai. The Thottiyar Nayakan community was divided into nine caste, out of 9,six established themselves in southern districts of Tamilnadu

1. Pullavar – Golah gentoo kambalatar
2. Correvar – Shephard of this tribe
3. Chellavar – Gentoo kambalatar
4. Yerrasimavar – Yeddia Kambalatar.
5. Vullakavar - Capilliar Kambalatar
6. Tokalavar - Veda kambalatar

¹⁹ Bharatha Pandian M,Bodinayakanur Zamin Varalaru ,(Tamil),peraiyur,1989,pp.21-23.

²⁰ T.B.S.S.C.S.Vadamalai Rajapandiyar,Zamindar Bodinayakanur.25.10.2024.

They did not inter marry beyond their Professional caste ²¹They would never tolerate impunity ,a deviation from orthodoxy was viewed seriously. Priestly class took care of religious matter. This caste purohiths were called *Kambili Nayak and Cudangg Nayak*. They were considered to be custodians of the caste. Their word was the law of the land²²

The kambalathar bore the “ Gento “appellation of Nayak as Amma Nayak, Bodinayak etc. Their language was Telugu but Tamil remained as their common language for communication²³

Kambalathar was named because they used *kambili* (woolen carpet) in their caste meetings and rituals. Which was spread on and a *kallasam* (small mudpot) filled with water containing Neem leaves was placed during the time of settling disputes²⁴

The priest were offered with *Inam* lands and farmers of the area are supposed cultivate their lands free of cost ²⁵quietly Brahminical influences penetrated into their social customs. The Sanskrit and shastra of Brahmins gradually modified zamindari beliefs they were also granted *Inam* lands for rendering religious duties to zamindars. Zamindars employed Brahmins to perform yagas. They were well versed in Sanskrit and Vedas. They read verses of Ramayana²⁶

The Then Madurai collector Levinge reported that,in Bodinayakanur a Brahmin preist employed by the zamindar was granted Inam land worth more than rupees 1000 in 1863²⁷.

²¹ Survey Report of Madurai and Dindigul Provinces,13 January 1817,M.C,R.Vol.9084,pp.11-12.

²² G.O.No.1682,R.D.(Confidential),19 July1915.

²³ Ibid.,p.17.

²⁴ Edgar Thurston,Caste and Tribes of South India,Vol.VII.Madras 1909,p.190.

²⁵ Estates Land Act Committee,Oral Evidence,Part II,Madras,1938,pp.251-252.

²⁶ G.O.No 1990,R.D.,22 May 1896.

²⁷ Ibid.No.72,13 January ,1863.

Women in Zamindari System:

Women were often isolated and restricted from the society her first menstruation was considered as pollution. A temporary hut was built at the outskirts of the village. It was guarded by people called Chakkliar for 15 days the hut was burndown and the pot used by her was broken²⁸. Public appearance of the women in zamindari families were forbidden in social and public appearances segregation of women was common feature²⁹

The *Gosha* system received greater attention. Gosha system is covering the entire body and forbidden to appear before strangers. Intercaste marriage was strictly prohibited ,violations were strictly dealt with ,rigid caste customs made woman submissive and isolated. They laboured the males and their families.³⁰

Marriage:

Marriage was arranged and ratified by kambili Nayak are priest with the approval of both marrying parties to temporary pandals. One for the groom other for the pride with the leaves of Pangoo trees. The Bride groom presented seven kalam of Cambu (one Kalam) is equal to eight liters to the bride). They march in a procession to the bride's house and give away beetlal nuts to the people.³¹

The Thali or the Nuptial card was tied around the bride's neck by a elderly women of the groom's family on behalf of bride groom, then both the families will have feast for several days. *urumi* a special drum was beaten through out the marriage by urumikaran. *Inam* lands was offered to them in return for their services.³²

²⁸ Francis,W.,Madras District Gazatteers,Madura,Vol.I,Government of Madras,1884,p.107.

²⁹ G.O.No.61,R.D.,19 January 1888.

³⁰ Ibid.,No.1682,R.D.,(Confidential),19 July 1915,.

³¹ Survey Report of Madurai and Dindigul Provinces,13 January 1817,M.C,R.Vol.9084,p.13.

³² G.O.No.1990.R.D.,22 May 1896.

Zamindars spent enormous amount of money on marriage functions to establish their Social Status. In 1874 the marriages of minor zamindar of Bodinayakanur and his brother was celebrated for a whopping sum of Rupees sixty thousand and all the resources of the zamindari were diverted for this purpose. The evil system of child marriage existed among zamindars. The discouragement of female education resulted in early marriages. They had a custom of ear boring for both male and female³³

Succession And Funeral Ceremonies:

After death of zamindars a new successor was the nominated. The boy was recognized as a new zamindar. The heir received Patta of the state which marks the important event of succession.³⁴ The successor was taken in a grand procession. In 1880 during the succession of Bodiayakanur zamindar a grand celebration was conducted at huge cost in which British officials too were present. He should not show any grief of the death of his father throughout the possession urumikaran played a mournful music marking sorrow and grief³⁵

The corpse was burnt on a pile of sandal wood. On the third day bones and ashes were collected, washed with milk and submerged into the river³⁶

Religion:

Zamindars of Madurai district are mostly Vaishnavites. Popular Goddesses were Jakkamma, Bommakka.. The ceremonies included bullock cart race. They spent large amount in performing yagnas and ceremonies at palani temple. The repeated process of performing ceremonies to their deities cost heavy financial strain to the treasury of zamindar. They Pilgrimaged to leading temples far away places like Tirupathi, Palani and Madurai Meenakshi.

³³ P.B.R.,No.10947,12 December 1876.

³⁴ Ward,B.S., Geographical and Statistical Memoir of the province of Madura &Dindigul,VoIII,Madura collectorate press,Madura.1895,p.64.

³⁵ G.O.No.1990,R.D.,22 May 1896.

³⁶ Ibid.,p.178.

They conducted festivals and offered huge amount of money as donations.³⁷ The zamindar of Bodinayakanur donated Rs 500 and offered Valuable prices to the priest of Sringeri Mutt³⁸

The zamindarini of Bodinayakanur, kamulammal maintained a Hospital, Victoria Memorial high school, library at Bodinayakanur. She introduced the practice of collecting a special tax called *Mahimai* to maintain the institutions. She was also a pious religious lady³⁹

Conclusion:

The Revenue system known as zamindari system was in practice form 1802 to 1949. It's impact in Madurai district Underwent different over tones. Witnessed confrontation of British and native palayakar. Failure of Mittasdar system. Earnest desire of the Government to continue zamindari system with payment of peshcush to the Government. The Economic, political, Social Non-comitance policies adopted by zamindars of Bodinayakaur made peasants suffer in the hands of intermediates. Which proved zamindars as pests and parasites to the peasants instead of being their protectors.

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³⁷ Ibid.,No.3501,25 April 1884.

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